

GREI Data Packaging Standards Comparison Matrix

Criteria	Data Package v2	RO-Crate	BagIt	CSV on the Web (CSVW)	Croissant (MLCommons)
Specification & Governance	JSON-based container format (datapackage.json). Actively maintained by Frictionless Data Working Group. Version 2 released 2024 with versioning guarantees. Open governance via OKFN + Frictionless community WG.	JSON-LD packaging of research objects based on schema.org. Governed by RO-Crate community under Research Object Initiative. W3C-aligned design.	IETF RFC 8493 (standardized). Mature and stable. Maintained by Library of Congress + digital preservation community.	W3C Recommendation (2015). Maintained by W3C CSVW WG (no major updates since recommendation).	Open JSON-LD spec built on schema.org/Dataset. Governed by MLCommons community with open GitHub repo and RFC process.
Primary Purpose / Model	General-purpose dataset descriptor + table schema + validation rules. Lightweight, extensible, machine-readable.	Package any digital object + metadata for research object publication. Focus on provenance, workflows, and reproducibility.	Packaging and file transfer (bag of files + manifest checksums). Focus on integrity, not semantics.	Provides metadata model and conversion rules for CSV files to RDF/JSON-LD. Emphasizes semantic web interoperability.	Describes ML datasets, resources, features, licensing, and loading hints. Designed for ML toolchains and dataset discovery.
Technical Capabilities	Includes Table Schema (field types, constraints, missing values, relationships) and Table Dialect (CSV parsing). Validation libraries available. Supports versioning and community schemas.	Rich contextual metadata (provenance, authorship, software used). No built-in schema/field validation, but can reference external profiles.	Simple manifests (checksums + fetch.txt). No schema validation or semantics.	Describes columns, datatypes, relationships, and links to vocabularies. Validation via JSON-LD and RDF tooling.	Focus on dataset structure for ML (e.g., splits, modalities). No low-level tabular validation, but strong integration with schema.org.
Tooling & Ecosystem	Mature Python & R libs (frictionless-py, frictionless-r), CLI tools, validation engine. Rust validator in development. Used in Zenodo (as export format), GBIF, BCO-DMO.	Tooling: ro-crate-py, ro-crate-js, exporters in Zenodo, WorkflowHub. Browser-based editors exist.	Widely implemented in preservation tools (Library of Congress BagIt-Java, Bagger, APTTrust).	Implementations in RDF libraries, CSV validators. Limited recent tool development.	Python mlcroissantlibrary, web-based editor, validator, integrations emerging (Dataverse, Hugging Face Datasets).
Adoption / Community	Used by thousands of researchers and major infrastructures (GBIF, BCO-DMO, Movebank, NIH commons, Dryad). Active developer & user community.	Adopted in workflow registries, reproducibility projects (WorkflowHub, ELIXIR). Recommended for FAIR digital objects.	Dominant for digital preservation and file transfer (used by DPN, APTTrust, Chronopolis).	Adoption mainly in open data/semantic web projects. Less common in repository pipelines.	New but growing adoption: Dataverse exposing exports; Hugging Face evaluating; supported by Google Dataset Search, Kaggle.
Performance & Scalability	Validates large tabular data; Rust validator improves speed. Declarative workflows make long-term reproducibility easier.	Scales well for complex objects, but size/verbosity can be heavy.	Highly scalable for file packages (used for multi-TB datasets).	Not optimized for huge tables; validation depends on RDF stack performance.	Lightweight JSON-LD; scales well for metadata but does not handle heavy data validation.
Extensibility	Highly modular. supports community schemas (e.g., Camtrap DP, Darwin Core DP).	Very extensible. any schema.org term can be added.	Extension possible but limited to manifests.	Extensible through RDF vocabularies.	Supports extensions through schema.org + custom MLCommons terms.
Implementation Considerations	Low barrier: one JSON file per dataset + libraries in common languages. Requires integration of validation step in repos.	Higher barrier: requires JSON-LD literacy, mapping to schema.org terms, more metadata effort.	Easy to implement for file integrity, but no semantics. would need pairing with other metadata system.	Requires mapping of CSVs to RDF and vocabulary definitions. potentially complex.	Still evolving. repos would need to implement Croissant exporters/importers, but leverages schema.org for discoverability.
Tabular vs. Non-Tabular Data	Strong focus on tabular data (schemas, constraints, validation). Can include non-tabular files but less prescriptive about them.	Handles both tabular and non-tabular data equally. suited to packaging mixed research objects (data, code, workflows).	Format-agnostic. just packages files (tabular or not) with manifests.	Tabular-focused; optimized for CSV/TSV with RDF mappings. Non-tabular data not well supported.	Supports both but optimized for ML-style datasets (images, audio, text + labels); limited schema support for tabular constraints.